

PRESSURE-DEPENDENT CONSTITUTIVE AND FAILURE MODEL FOR LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

This paper presents a non-linear, pressure-dependent, three dimensional constitutive law and associated failure criteria for laminated composites with UD plies. The failure criteria result from a physical model for each failure mode. In-situ strengths are used for matrix failure and fibre kinking. The model is validated against experimental data.

Keywords: Pressure dependence, Constitutive law, Hydrostatic pressure, Failure criteria, In-situ strength

INTRODUCTION

Experimental data for several composites shows a pressure-dependence of the Young's and shear moduli, and of the strength – Figure 1(a,b). While several published failure criteria capture the pressure-dependence of the matrix failure mode through Mohr-Coulomb type criteria, fewer capture the known pressure-dependence of the fibre-kinking strength. Even fewer embody the pressure-dependence of the elastic moduli and matrix yielding.

For most experimental data published, the dependence of initial (linear elastic) moduli with pressure can be approximated reasonably with a linear function, see e.g. Figure 1(b). However, many authors identify two separate regions with different slopes [1-3], with the kink between the regions related to the dependence of the glass transition temperature on pressure.

The dependence of the elastic moduli on hydrostatic pressure is due to the polymeric resin. This dependence can be predicted with good accuracy for a wide range of polymers [3] using a model proposed by Birch [4]. Birch's model is simple and only requires the moduli at atmospheric pressure and the Poisson's ratio of the polymer:

$$\begin{aligned} E &= E_o + \eta_E p_r & \text{with} & \quad \eta_E = 2(5 - 4\nu)(1 - \nu), \\ G &= G_o + \eta_G p_r & \text{with} & \quad \eta_G = \frac{3(3 - 4\nu)}{2(1 + \nu)}, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where E and G are the initial Young's and shear moduli, respectively, E_o and G_o are the Young's and shear moduli (in the elastic region) at a reference pressure, respectively, p_r is the pressure (relative to the pressure at which E_o and G_o are measured) and ν is the elastic Poisson's ratio.

The slope coefficients η_E and η_G for the composite can either be measured experimentally, or deduced from the slope coefficients for the polymer using a suitable micromechanical model. Hine et al. [2] compared the two approaches for a glass/epoxy using Wilczynski's model [5], and obtained a good agreement. If the slope coefficients of the composite are obtained from the slope coefficients of the polymer, then those latter coefficients can be either measured experimentally or calculated using Birch's model [4]. Values of the slope parameters η_E and η_G measured experimentally for different polymers and different composites are compiled in Ref. [6].

Figure 1: Effect of pressure on (a) shear response, and (b) initial shear modulus, [7]

The strength of composites is greatly affected by hydrostatic pressure. Experimental data shows that the failure stress increases linearly with pressure until a given pressure, after which the growth rate appears to decrease [7-9]. The increase in strength can also be observed in pure polymer, see Figure 2. Physically, the increase in strength with pressure can be attributed to two separate factors. Firstly, the compressive stresses close micro-crack tips thus allowing for both friction and mechanical locking between the faces of the microcracks, resulting in a strengthening effect. Secondly, the volumetric deformation induced by the hydrostatic pressure increases the entanglement of the polymer chains, which may further delay failure.

Figure 2: Experimental failure points for an epoxy resin, after [9], and predictions using Raghava and modified von Mises criteria

MODEL DETAILS

Constitutive model

The constitutive model, presented in more detail elsewhere [6], is formulated at the ply level. The ply strains $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are related to the stresses $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ in the same ply through Hooke's law for orthotropic materials,

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \gamma_{12} \\ \gamma_{23} \\ \gamma_{31} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_1 & -\nu_{12}/E_1 & -\nu_{13}/E_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & 1/E_2 & -\nu_{23}/E_2 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & 1/E_3 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & 1/G_{12} & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & 1/G_{23} & 0 \\ & & & & & 1/G_{31} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \\ \tau_{12} \\ \tau_{23} \\ \tau_{31} \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

All Young's and shear moduli, but E_1 , are defined as $E = E^o(\varepsilon_{eq}) + \eta p$ where E is a modulus, E^o is the corresponding modulus at atmospheric pressure, ε_{eq} is an equivalent strain, η is a material property which can be obtained experimentally (Figure 1(b)), and p is the transverse hydrostatic pressure.

Matrix failure

The matrix failure criterion used here is part of the LaRC05 failure criteria [10], and is presented in more detail elsewhere [6].

The strengths associated with matrix-dominated failure in a composite are structural properties, dependent on the thickness of the ply, and on the neighbouring plies in the laminate. Under the same stress state (averaged over ply thickness), the conditions for the propagation of micro-cracks are more favourable for the case of a UD laminate than for a thin ply in a multi-axial laminate neighboured by 0° plies. The thickness of the ply and the presence of neighbouring plies change the boundary conditions of the fracture mechanics problem for crack growth, see Figure 3, thus leading to different strengths depending on the ply, as detailed in Table 1.

Figure 3: Slit crack considered for in-situ effects. (a) ply in a UD laminate; (b) thin outer ply; (c) thin embedded ply; (d) thick embedded ply

Table 1: Formulae for in-situ strengths, after [6]

	<i>Transverse tensile strength</i>	<i>Longitudinal shear strength</i>	<i>Transverse shear strength</i>
UD	Y_T	S_L	$S_T = Y_C \cos(\alpha_o) \left(\sin(\alpha_o) + \frac{\cos(\alpha_o)}{\tan(2\alpha_o)} \right)$
Thick embedded	$1.12\sqrt{2}Y_T$	$\sqrt{2}S_L$	$\sqrt{2}S_T$
Thin embedded	$\sqrt{8G_{IC}^L/\pi h \Lambda}$	$\sqrt{8G_{IC}^L G_{12}/\pi h}$	$\sqrt{8G_{IC}^L G_{12}/\pi h}$
Thin outer	$\sqrt{4G_{IC}^T/\pi h \Lambda}$	$\sqrt{4G_{IC}^T G_{12}/\pi h}$	$\sqrt{8G_{IC}^T G_{12}/\pi h}$

with $\Lambda = 2 \left(\frac{1}{E_2} - \frac{\nu_{21}^2}{E_1} \right)$ and $h' = h/\cos \alpha_o$. See also Figure 4.

Figure 4: Traction components acting on the matrix fracture plane, from [10]

The matrix failure criterion proposed here is a variation of the Mohr-Coulomb criterion, as first proposed for composites by Puck and co-workers [11], and reads

$$FI_M = \left(\frac{\tau_T}{S_T^{is} - \eta_T \sigma_N} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_L}{S_L^{is} - \eta_L \sigma_N} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_N \rangle_+}{Y_T^{is}} \right)^2, \quad (3)$$

with failure being predicted when $FI_M \geq 1$. The last term in the criterion represents the contribution from the positive normal traction in opening the cracks. Therefore, this criterion is intended to be applicable for both tensile and compressive matrix failure.

In Eq. 3, τ_L , τ_T and σ_N are the traction components in the (potential) fracture plane, see Figure 4, and are obtained by stress transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_N &= \frac{\sigma_2 + \sigma_3}{2} + \frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2} \cos(2\alpha) + \tau_{23} \sin(2\alpha) \\ \tau_T &= -\frac{\sigma_2 - \sigma_3}{2} \sin(2\alpha) + \tau_{23} \cos(2\alpha) \\ \tau_L &= \tau_{12} \cos(\alpha) + \tau_{31} \sin(\alpha) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where α is the angle that maximizes FI_M , and is obtained numerically by evaluating the function at selected angles in the interval $0^\circ \leq \alpha < 180^\circ$ as per Refs. [10, 12, 13]. The particular value of α for pure transverse compression, α_o , is a material property that can be measured experimentally. Several authors have observed that the fracture angle for either glass or carbon composites is typically $51^\circ \leq \alpha_o \leq 55^\circ$ [10, 14, 15].

The slope or friction coefficients η_T and η_L in Eq. 3 are introduced to account for the effect of pressure on the failure response. Their effect is that of increasing the respective shear strengths in the presence of a compressive normal traction and reducing the respective shear strengths in the presence of a tensile normal traction. The slope or friction coefficient η_T is obtained from the pure transverse compression test as a function of α_o [10],

$$\eta_T = -\frac{1}{\tan(2\alpha_o)}, \quad (5)$$

while the slope or friction coefficient η_L is an independent material property that needs to be measured experimentally. Finally, the McCauley brackets $\langle \bullet \rangle_+$ in Eq. 3 are defined as $\langle x \rangle_+ = \max\{0, x\}$.

Fibre kinking

Fibre kinking is assumed to result from shear-dominated matrix failure in a misaligned frame, under significant longitudinal compression, see Figure 5. However, if the longitudinal compression is not significant, the shear-dominated matrix failure on the misaligned frame results in fibre splitting but not necessarily in fibre kinking. The criteria proposed here for fibre kinking and for splitting use the same failure index equation written as

$$FI_{KINK} = FI_{SPLIT} = \left(\frac{\tau_{23}^m}{S_T^{is} - \eta_T \sigma_2^m} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}^m}{S_L^{is} - \eta_L \sigma_2^m} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_2^m \rangle_+}{Y_T^{is}} \right)^2. \quad (6)$$

The two failure modes are then distinguished based on the magnitude of longitudinal compression with $\sigma_1 \leq -X_c/2$ indicating fibre kinking and $\sigma_1 \geq -X_c/2$ signifying fibre splitting. The rotated coordinate systems relevant for the description of a kink band are shown in Figure 5. For more details, refer to Ref. [6].

Fibre tensile failure

The maximum stress failure criterion has been shown to correlate well with existing experimental data [16] for fibre tensile failure. Therefore, the maximum stress criterion is here used to predict this failure mode:

$$FI_{FT} = \frac{\langle \sigma_1 \rangle_+}{X_T}. \quad (7)$$

Figure 5: Physical model for kink-band formation

APPLICATIONS

The failure criteria are applied to predict the biaxial failure envelope of a $(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ)$ s AS4/3501-6 laminate, from the first World-Wide Failure Exercise [16]. The input properties for the model can be found in Ref. [17]. The predictions from the model are compared to experimental data and to those of Puck's model [11] in Figure 6. For the tensile-tensile quadrant, it can be seen that there is an excellent correlation between the current predictions, Puck's predictions and the experiments for final failure. In the same quadrant, the current predictions for initial failure differ slightly from Puck's, and are in better agreement with the experimental data. This is related to the use of the in-situ strength model. For the compression-compression quadrant, both Puck and LaRC05 over-predict the experimental results, but LaRC05 more so. However, the experimental points correspond in this case to buckling failure of the specimens [16], a failure mode not considered by either Puck's model or LaRC05.

Figure 6: Biaxial failure envelope of a $(90^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/0^\circ)_s$ AS4/3501-6 laminate

Figure 7(a) shows the predicted τ_{12} vs. σ_2 with $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3$ failure envelope for a T300/PR319 composite (material properties in Table 2), together with the corresponding experimental results [7, 18]. It can be seen that the increase in strength with hydrostatic pressure is correctly captured.

The non-linear in-plane shear response of the same composite under $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = -600$ MPa is compared to experimental data in Figure 7(b). It can be observed that the increase in elastic modulus due to hydrostatic pressure is correctly reproduced. The non-linear response up to failure is acceptable, but clearly more experimental data would be required to fully assess the merits of the non-linear model.

Figure 7: (a) Failure envelope for τ_{12} vs. σ_2 with $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3$ and (b) stress vs. strain response for τ_{12} vs. γ_{12} with $\sigma_1 = \sigma_2 = \sigma_3 = -600$ MPa

Table 2: Material properties used for the predictions in Figure 7

	<i>T300/ PR319</i>
E_1 (GPa)	129
E_2 (GPa)	5.6
G_{12} (GPa)	1.33
ν_{12}	0.318
ν_{23}	0.5
η_E	16
η_G	0.2
η_L	0.082
X_T (MPa)	1378
X_C (MPa)	950
Y_T (MPa)	40
Y_C (MPa)	125
α_o (°)	53
S_L (MPa)	97

CONCLUSIONS

The constitutive and failure models developed can successfully predict the nonlinear response and strength of composites under tri-axial stress states, including high superposed pressures. The failure models distinguish between different failure modes, include in-situ strength effects, and represent crack accumulation and propagation through fracture mechanics.

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